

ANNEXURE F: INFORMED CONSENT

STUDY TITLE: MONITORING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE 95-95-95 STRATEGY IN TSHWANE: A QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF LOCAL PROGRESS, 2018-2024.

Principal Investigator: Xolisile Cynthia Moyo

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1. Purpose of the Study

You are invited to participate in this research study which aims to monitor the progress of the 95-95-95 HIV targets in Tshwane, Gauteng. The study will use routine program data and, where necessary, information from health workers involved in HIV service delivery.

2. Procedures

If you agree to participate: You will be asked to complete a short questionnaire with 14 questions. Questions will relate to your professional experiences in HIV service delivery and program implementation. No personal or identifying information will be collected beyond what is necessary for the study.

3. Voluntary Participation

Your participation is completely voluntary. You may refuse to participate or withdraw at any time without any negative consequences. Choosing not to participate will not affect your employment or professional responsibilities.

4. Risks and Discomforts

The study poses minimal risks.

Some questions may feel sensitive as they relate to HIV program implementation, but you may skip any question you are not comfortable answering.

5. Benefits

There may be no direct personal benefit to you. However, your input will contribute to improving HIV program monitoring and strengthening progress towards the 95-95-95 targets in Tshwane.

6. Confidentiality

All information you provide will be kept strictly confidential. Data will be coded and stored securely. No names or personal identifiers will appear in the study report or publications.

7. Contacts for Questions

If you have any questions about the study or your rights as a participant, please contact:

Researcher: Xolisile Cynthia Moyo

Supervisor: Dr Mudau A

Ethics Committee: Univen Ethics Committee

8. Consent Statement

By signing below, you acknowledge that:

You have read and understood the information provided.

You have had the opportunity to ask questions and they have been answered.

You voluntarily agree to participate in this study.

Participant's Name: _____

Signature: _____ Date: _____

Researcher's Name: _____

Signature: _____ Date: _____